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**ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ
ОЛИЙ ВА ЎРТА МАХСУС
ТАЪЛИМ ВАЗИРЛИГИ**

**НАМАНГАН ДАВЛАТ УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ
ИЛМИЙ АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**НАУЧНЫЙ ВЕСТНИК НАМАНГАНСКОГО
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТА**

2021 йил 9-сон

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Ушбу журнал 2019 йилдан бошлаб Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий аттестация комиссияси Раёсати қарори билан физика-математика, кимё, биология, фалсафа, филология ва педагогика фанлари бўйича Олий аттестация комиссиясининг диссертациялар асосий илмий натижаларини чоп этиш тавсия этилган илмий нашрлар рўйхатига киритилган.

“НамДУ илмий ахборотномаси–Научный вестник НамГУ” журнали Ўзбекистон Матбуот ва ахборот агентлигининг 17.05.2016 йилдаги 08-0075 рақамли гувоҳномаси ҳамда Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Администрацияси ҳузуридаги Ахборот ва оммавий коммуникациялар агентлиги (АОКА) томонидан 2020 йил 29 август куни 1106-сонли гувоҳнома га биноан чоп этилади. “НамДУ Илмий Ахборотномаси” электрон нашр сифатида халқаро стандарт туркум рақами (ISSN-2181-1458)га эга НамДУ Илмий-техникавий Кенгашининг 14.09.2021 йилдаги кенгайтирилган йигилишида муҳокама қилиниб, илмий тўплам сифатида чоп этишга рухсат этилган (**Баённома № 9**). Мақолаларнинг илмий савияси ва келтирилган маълумотлар учун муаллифлар жавобгар ҳисобланади.

НАМАНГАН ДАВЛАТ УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ-2021

08.00.00

**ИҚТИСОДИЁТ ФАHLАРИ
ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ
ECONOMIC SCIENCES**

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF STATE SUPPORT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS

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Abstract: *The article examines the foreign practice of organizing state support for the development of small business. The main tools used by the state for the development of small businesses are reflected on the example of a number of countries. On the basis of the study, the general features of foreign state support mechanisms are formulated.*

Keywords: *business, state regulation, foreign experience, small business, economy.*

**KICHIK TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH UCHUN DAVLAT QO'LLAB-
QUVVATLASHNING XORIJIY TAJRIBASI**

Iqtisod fanlari nomzodi, dotsent, Farg'ona politexnika instituti
Kurpayanidi Konstantin Ivanovich

Anastasiya. *Maqolada kichik biznesni rivojlantirishni davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlashni tashkil etishning xorijiy amaliyoti o'rganib chiqilgan. Kichik biznesni rivojlantirish uchun davlat tomonidan qo'llaniladigan asosiy vositalar bir qator mamlakatlar misolida aks ettirilgan. Tadqiqot asosida xorijiy davlatlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarining umumiy xususiyatlari shakllantirildi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *biznes, davlat tomonidan tartibga solish, xorijiy tajriba, kichik biznes, iqtisodiyot.*

**ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ ПОДДЕРЖКИ РАЗВИТИЯ МАЛОГО
БИЗНЕСА**

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Аннотация: *В статье исследуется зарубежная практика организации государственной поддержки развития малого предпринимательства. На примере ряда стран отражены основные инструменты, используемые государством для развития малого бизнеса. На основе исследования сформулированы общие черты зарубежных механизмов государственной поддержки.*

Ключевые слова: *бизнес, государственное регулирование, иностранный опыт, малое предпринимательство, экономика.*

Under conditions of effective and balanced state support, small business enterprises have the best possibilities to adapt during crisis phenomena. Since small enterprises quickly

enough occupy the spheres of activity in which big business is not interested, the functioning of the state economy depends on their development, it helps to overcome stagnation phenomena in the economic system of the country. To expand the sector of small business enterprises and their sustainable development it is very important to analyze the world experience of small business activity. Foreign experience convincingly testifies that small business enterprises develop rapidly, operate stably and efficiently in the developed countries of the world due to active state support at all levels of government. The state, in its turn, gets the growth of production volumes, reduction of tension in the labor market, balancing of different sectors of economy, cooperation of big and small business, forming of middle class of entrepreneurs, solving of social problems, increasing of competitiveness of national goods, increasing of revenues to the budgets of all levels at the expense of taxes. Therefore, small business is the basis for the stable development of the economy of any country. In France, the main influence on the development and stimulation of small business by the state authorities is concentrated on the improvement of managerial staff of small firms and the creation of legislative guarantees to prevent them from bankruptcy. In Spain, the government provides financial assistance to small businesses in case of shortage of its own funds. Developing Asian countries (Taiwan, Singapore, and Indonesia) made an economic breakthrough precisely at the expense of the rapid development of small businesses [1, p.2].

Singapore ranks 5th in the world in the development of small businesses due to the provision of tax benefits (especially in the early years of establishment of the enterprise), the constant reduction of interest on loans provided to small businesses, a large number of preferential lending programs, government funding for training and skills development of workers engaged in small businesses. Thanks to such support in Singapore there are about 140 thousand small and medium-sized enterprises, which is 90% of all companies in the country, which provide GDP growth of 5-6% per year [2, p.3].

Small business in China is developing very rapidly and successfully, as evidenced by the significant volume of low-cost goods produced by small businesses. The Chinese government has decided to reorient the country's economy from resource-intensive industries to small businesses, and also supports the development of enterprises in software development and the production of electrical goods. Small business development in China is regulated by the National Development and Reform Commission, which decides to stimulate the creation and development of certain types of small businesses, oversees tender auctions, which enable small businesses to receive government orders for the supply of goods and services [3, p.2].

It should be noted that there are 3 million small businesses in India, which employ up to 80% of the employees of the entire Indian industry. The main spheres of activity of small enterprises are farming, information and technological spheres. Government support plays an important role in the development of small businesses, and is provided at the federal and regional levels, and programs to support small businesses are developed for 5-10 years by the Planning Commission of India. The state support of small enterprises in India consists in development of export activity of small companies, granting tax and customs privileges, subsidies, reduction of rent rates and preferential financing [4, p.1].

In Japan, the share of small businesses is about 40%, which operate in the sectors of construction, light industry, and services. The benefits for small business development

depend on the status of the enterprise and the type of activity. State support for small business consists of state subsidies and loans for enterprise development, and the state acts as a guarantor when obtaining a loan from a bank. Japanese legislation strictly regulates the market value of all types of products, the government controls unreasonable price increases for raw materials, finished products and services, which promotes small business development in the country.

The peculiarity of state regulation of small business in Japan is manifested in the temporary nature of support for the development of certain branches or spheres of activity, which are of great importance for the development of the country or are in unfavorable economic conditions. Small enterprises are assisted in obtaining state orders for the supply of goods and services, whose share in the volume of state orders is 45%, and in the volume of other enterprises and organizations - 32%.

In Japan, the main attention of the state is paid to the development of entrepreneurial structures, the activities of which have a research nature, and the products are knowledge-intensive, competitive in world markets. An important issue of state influence on entrepreneurial activity is the provision of financial resources. The state pays special attention to the development and production of resource-saving technologies. Accordingly economic methods of assistance are applied, including privileges in taxation of entrepreneurial activity, preferential credits are provided; the system of assistance to development of priority directions of entrepreneurship is formed [5, p.2].

Priority areas of entrepreneurship [5, p.3]. Japan has created a climate most favorable to small business. The state support of small and medium-sized business in Japan is aimed at strengthening the weak economic places of such enterprises. On the basis of the law "On the basis of the policy of small and medium-sized enterprises". (1963), the country established a coherent system of legislation to provide comprehensive support for small businesses. Among the many laws aimed at supporting business in Japan, we should highlight the laws "On the Promotion of Modernization of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises", "On the Organization of Cooperatives of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises", "On the Management of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises". As a mechanism for implementing these laws, the government has set up a special body, the Advisory Council.

The state applies rather transparent forms of support, which stimulate the effective development of small business [6, p.3]. For example, a special procedure is established for financing small forms of economic activity. These enterprises are credited not only by regular commercial banks, but also by specially created state and private financial institutions. The national budget of Japan provides funds to support small businesses in the form of subsidies. They are distributed and monitored by the offices of small and medium-sized enterprises under the Ministry of Foreign Trade and Industry and the financial support fund.

Based on the existing business support legislation in Japan, three public financial funds have been established to provide financial support to small businesses: the Central Cooperative Bank for Trade and Industry, the People's Finance Corporation, and the State Small Business Finance Corporation [7, p.3]. A significant contribution to the financing of small and medium-sized businesses has been made by state and local governments of Japan, associations that perform the function of guaranteeing loans to small and medium-sized businesses. The State Corporation for Credit Insurance and Small Business Financing, joint-

stock companies for investment and development of small and medium-sized firms also have similar objectives. Such state custodial measures provide real support to small businesses that are not yet in a position to provide the funds they receive with personal property [8, p.2]. The analysis of mechanisms of support of small business in Japan testifies that the more considerable is the role of small business in economic life, the more various are the forms of its support [9, p.2]. Thus, the study of foreign mechanisms of state support allows us to reveal common features. They, in our opinion, include:

- rational distribution of functions between central, regional and local bodies of state power on the issues of small business support;
- formation and implementation of a comprehensive system of state and regional support programs;
- Allocations from the budgets of different levels for the implementation of programs to help small businesses;
- a combination of direct and indirect measures to support small businesses.

Thus, an analysis of global experience in the development and state support of small businesses shows that for the effective operation of all sectors of the economy it is essential to form a coherent system of state support for small business development, create a high-quality legal framework and eliminate the mismatch between national quantitative criteria for defining small business entities and the indicators used by developed countries.

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ИННОВАЦИОН ИҚТИСОДИЁТДА АЁЛЛАР ТАДБИРКОРЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ

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***Аннотация:** Ушбу мақолада инновацион иқтисодиётга ўтиш шароитида аёллар тадбиркорлигини ривожлантириш истиқболлари ёритилган. Муаллиф томонидан тадқиқот доирасида таклиф-мулохазалар келтирилган.*

***Калит сўзлар:** тадбиркорлик, ижтимоий соҳага йўналтирилган бизнес, хусусий тадбиркорлик, аёллар тадбиркорлиги, оилавий бизнес, касаначилик, ҳунармандчилик*

ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЖЕНСКОГО ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА В ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ

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***Аннотация:** В статье рассматриваются перспективы развития женского предпринимательства в условиях перехода к инновационной экономике. Автор вносит предложения в области исследования.*

***Ключевые слова:** предпринимательство, социально ориентированный бизнес, частное предпринимательство, женское предпринимательство, семейный бизнес, надомный труд, ремесла*

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF WOMEN'S ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN AN INNOVATIVE ECONOMY

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***Abstract:** The article examines the prospects for the development of women's entrepreneurship in the context of the transition to an innovative economy. The author makes suggestions in the field of research.*

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